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The effectiveness of digital components used in physical activity interventions targeted to youth: a focus meta-analysis on step count measure in the the DigitAI Lifelong pREvention (DARE) project

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INTRODUCTION

Previous studies have shown that daily step count could be a valid and fast measure for physical activity (PA) assessment¹. Different interventions using digital tools attempt to increase step number in young populations, but it is not clear whether there is an overall positive effect. The aim of this study, which is part of an umbrella review performed within the DigitAI Lifelong pREvention (DARE) project, is to provide an overview of the effectiveness of digital interventions targeted to schoolers on PA increase, with a focus on the step count.

RESULTS

Generality

A total of 41 reviews/MAs and 61 extracted RCTs were analyzed. Data extraction allowed to obtain eighteen observations from eight studies. Average daily step count across studies ranged between 2,655 and 11,892. In this work, results derived from the use of the fixed effect model are showed.

MA results

Results of the MA show a positive overall effect on daily steps increase, with a MD of 799, and a 95% CI 694.8-903.1; high heterogeneity (I^2 90.7%) was found out (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Effect of digital-based interventions on step count.

Publication bias

A small-study effect was evidenced, with lower precision studies reporting stronger effects (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Funnel plot of the relationship between estimate precision and effect size.

Bibliography

1. Hall, K. S. et al. Systematic review of the prospective association of daily step counts with risk of mortality, cardiovascular disease, and dysglycemia. *Int. J. Behav. Nutr. Phys. Act.* 17, 78 (2020)

METHODS

A systematic review (SR) was conducted on SRs and meta-analyses (MAs) that collected Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) using digital tools for increasing PA in healthy students aged 6-17. A MA was then performed on those RCTs that measured mean daily steps via wearable devices; both fixed and random effect models were used, and estimates were obtained as Mean Differences (MDs) and 95% Confidence Intervals (CIs). Subgroup analyses were performed to explore heterogeneity, and small study effects and publication bias were assessed.

Subgroup analysis

The sensitivity analysis shows effectiveness in: more recent studies; populations from Australia/New Zealand and Asia; youngers; school/community setting; short term assessment; when the control group is an alternative intervention; when wearables or a mix were used as intervention delivery tools; studies adding non-digital components; and when Yamax pedometer was used as a measurement tool (Table 1).

Table 1. Subgroup analysis of the effect of digital-based interventions on step count.

	WMD	LCI	UCI
Publication date			
>=2018	830,7	723,9	937,5
<2018	175,8	-297,6	649,2
Continent			
Europe	-884,5	-1244,0	-524,9
America	239,2	-381,3	859,6
Oceania	1208,0	616,0	1800,0
Asia	967,6	855,0	1080,1
School age			
Youngers	830,7	723,9	937,5
Olders	175,8	-297,6	649,2
Setting 2cat			
School/Community	861,2	753,7	968,8
Home	-156,1	-577,2	265,0
Follow-up			
Short term (<=3 m)	864,1	756,1	972,1
Medium term	-226,2	-818,1	365,6
Long term	41,1	-492,4	574,6
Control group			
Alternative interve	939,5	827,4	1051,5
No intervention	-96,2	-379,0	186,7
Digital component			
Wearable	940,0	829,5	1050,6
Web	-1291,5	-1833,1	-749,9
Mix	989,7	475,7	1503,7
Gamification	-868,0	-1437,3	-298,7
Non-digital component used			
Yes	953,6	842,5	1064,6
No	-329,2	-629,3	-29,1
Device for step measurement			
Pedometer	874,6	767,1	982,1
Other	-367,6	-789,7	54,6
Device model			
Yamax	955,4	846,1	1064,7
Walk4Life	-1595,9	-2202,7	-989,1
Actigraph	243,4	-385,7	872,4
Other	-846,6	-1409,5	-283,6

CONCLUSIONS

This MA shows that digital-based interventions are overall effective in increasing step count of schoolers. Some considerations have to be done on what could be improved to guarantee effectiveness in older students; in interventions conducted in a home environment; on a medium or long term follow-up; when the web or gamification are used as intervention delivery methods; and when devices for step measures other than pedometers are used. Moreover, it would be recommended to increase studies on European populations of children and adolescents, and consider to add also non-digital components in the intervention procedure. All these aspects will be taken into account in the DARE project, in order to build correct models for PA enhancement in scholars, and in particular for step number.